

Original Research Article

M. K. Gandhi and Educational Philosophy**Dr. Omshiva V. Ligade¹ and Dr. Arvind V. Kadam²**^{1,2}Shivjagruiti Senior College, Nalegaon Tq. Chakur District: Latur 413524 Maharashtra, IndiaCorresponding author E-mail: ¹omshivaligade@gmail.com; ²kdmavind38@gmail.com

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Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi's primary education was the main source of his education. Gandhi education undertakes the challenging task of preparing students to become moral, independent, social, productive and responsible citizens of the future, which can be achieved by equipping young people with skills. Education helps them become self-employed and thus helps solve the problem of unemployment. Gandhi believed that a child's education should help him reach his full potential and become a fully-fledged individual. In this way, a whole and harmonious character can be the purpose of life, which is also true. Reading is not where learning starts or ends, it just means the man or woman is educated.¹

M. K. Gandhi's basic philosophy² of education includes:

1. Instruction must be in the mother language.
2. Education should teach children to value people.
3. Education should create harmony between children's body, mind, heart and soul.
4. Education for every child from the age of seven to fourteen should be free
5. compulsory and universal
6. Reading alone is not the same as education.
7. Crafts should be used in education as a teaching tool to help kids become self-sufficient as they grow in life.
8. Citizens who have received an education should be capable, productive, and empowered. All of a child's concealed skills should be developed via education in keeping with the society to which he belongs.
9. Education should be self-sufficient with some effective work.
10. A financially independent life and self-reliant life should result from education.
11. All work should be divided according to a production process or business and have a good relationship with the business.
12. This work should enable children to have a rich career with good work.

M. K. Gandhi emphasized that essential foundation of education is the inseparability of learning and labor.³ Separation of education and work will lead to injustice. In a strong society, education should provide people with the skills and attitudes necessary to adapt to changes and participate in social change work. This helps relieve depression, melancholy, anxiety and suicidal thoughts in teenagers.

Gandhi felt that in order to ensure his future, young people should be able to learn a profession by engaging in some form of commerce or trade alongside receiving an education. Therefore, he advocated the education of self-reliance and viability as the main purpose of education. His goal is to make his children work, but he hopes that every child can earn money while studying and gain some knowledge while working. He suggested that leadership should be accompanied by vocational training.

According to M. K. Gandhi, education should cultivate every component of a harmonious character. Gandhi wished for all children to progress to be individuals who recognize their true selves. Gandhi wrote, Personal development is building character and preparing one for self-realization and God's fulfilment. M. K. Gandhi's primary education was limited to primary and lower classes.

Gandhi's primary education was business-oriented, value-oriented and mass-oriented. It should be mentioned that these are still significant needs in our nation's educational system. Content in academic courses needs to be connected to actions and performance. Therefore, his teaching used to be practical. Its goal is to get the child ready for work, exploration, and research so he can grow up to be a productive adult and a significant contributor to society on all levels. The Gandhi Curriculum covers a broad range of subjects in terms of teaching activities, such as art, music, general science, social studies, arithmetic, basic crafts, and also the mother tongue⁴. He added, the curriculum of classes 1 to 5 should be the same for boys and girls. After this, boys should learn some handicrafts, and girls should learn domestic sciences.

Today's education system is a means of increasing the value of consumers, products, unfair competition and violence. Growing concerns about the destruction of morality, youth conflict, environmental crimes, and increasing scepticism in society have led to the need to promote Native American heritage and ways of life. Gandhi saw this development fifty years ago and suggested a new method for elementary schooling.⁵

M. K. Gandhi also said that mainstream education includes physical education through music as well as principles of cleanliness, hygiene and nutrition. Gandhi thought that through education, students would become resilient, confident, and beneficial to their parents and the nation. Gandhi also said that his system would be the same for everyone and would also bring harmony to society.

M. K. Gandhi did not approve of memorization, thought wrongly, and gave importance to handicrafts and work as education. She hopes to create some local handicrafts as a learning environment for children, so that their bodies, minds and souls can create harmony and fulfil their desires for the future. Therefore, Gandhi's teaching is different from the existing teaching.

In his Teaching, M. K. Gandhi underlined the significance of the following principles:⁶

1. To attain wisdom, the mind and body must be trained.
2. Teaching reading should come before teaching writing.
3. More time should be devoted to learning by doing.
4. Learning through experience should be encouraged.
5. There should be correlation between the methods of teaching and learning experiences.

Conclusion

M. K. Gandhi's 'Basic Education' was job-oriented, value-based, and mass-oriented. Here it is important to mention that these are still significant needs in our nation's educational system. According to his educational plan, information needs to be connected to action and real-world situations. Gandhi's primary education is the foundation of his educational philosophy and his curriculum is therefore the workplace. Its goal is to get the child ready for work, exploration, and research so he can grow up to be a productive adult and a significant contributor to society on all levels. Gandhi included the mother tongue in his literary teaching activities. Gandhi's philosophy of education is that the development of a child's character is more important than literacy or general knowledge. In other words, he believes in life-centered education and child-centered education.

References

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